

A NEW SENSOR TECHNOLOGY FOR THE SONIFICATION OF PROXIMITY AND TOUCH IN CLOSED-LOOP AUDITORY INTERACTION

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ABSTRACT

The Italian word *sentire* [sen'ti:re] means both to hear and to feel. What if one could “hear” closeness or distance to another person? The paper presents a new sensor technology for sonifying proximity and touch which we have developed for *Sentire*, a digital system that mediates between bodily movements and musical sounds. Using this technology, inter-body proximity and touch can be sensed wirelessly and mapped to an algorithmic sound environment in real time, allowing for a closed-loop auditory interaction between two or more people in a physical environment. We describe its iterative and incremental development within the interdisciplinary research project “Social interaction through sound feedback–*Sentire*,” which combines (artistic) human-computer interaction, sonic interaction design and real-world research. The prototype and its underlying sensor technology—based on electro-quasistatic coupling—have been successfully used in couple therapy, serving as both a framework for usability testing and to investigate the relationship between sound, sociality and therapy.

1. INTRODUCTION

Since the implementation of protective measures to counter the global COVID-19 pandemic, interpersonal distance has gained new implications. So-called social distancing caused a shift in perceptions of personal space. Proxemics, a field that studies the human perception of personal space, dates back to 1966, when anthropologist Edward Hall classified four culturally dependent zones of interpersonal distance: intimate (less than 0.5m), personal (0.5m–1.2m), social (1.2m–3.6m) and public (3.5m–7.6m). According to Hall [1], these zones strongly influence how people interact with each other. Greenberg et al. [2] point out the relevance of Hall’s studies in Ubiquitous Computing. Although they refer more generally to inter-entity distance rather than inter-body distance, they underline the necessity, and possibilities, of measuring proximity for interaction design.

Established systems for measuring physical proximity and using it in the digital domain typically rely on infrared or ultrasonic sensors. These systems measure the distance at

discrete points and require a clear field of vision. They are thus disadvantageous for dyadic interaction. The sonification of inter-body proximity includes different research fields ranging from (sonic) interaction design, including sound design [3–8], and embodied interaction [9, 10] to human-computer interaction design [11, 12]. Although these fields all contribute to the interdisciplinary character of our research, this paper focuses on the aspects of the underlying sensor technology developed within our project, called “Social interaction through sound feedback – *Sentire*” to systematically investigate its applicability in the context of therapy.

First, we present related work and the theoretical background of proximity sensing based on inter-body coupling. Next, we describe the soft- and hardware we developed over an iterative and incremental process. Finally, we present the results of prototype testing in couple therapy¹ sessions.

2. RELATED WORK AND THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

2.1 Sensing Human Proximity and Touch

At the time of writing, we are unaware of any other sensor system used to sonify proximity and touch between humans as the subject of academic research. However, there have been interfaces developed that explore the relationship between touch and sound feedback or that use proximity sensors in interactive scenarios. *Skintimacy* [13] uses skin conductivity to sonify touch events between two or more humans; Müller et al. investigate its influence on intimate behaviour in the context of performance and musical interaction. A similar system, called *Closer*, was developed for examining embodied interaction in health care, though no results were published [14]. *Freqtrix Drums* is a musical interface that can quantitatively detect skin contact by measuring skin resistance which is related to touch pressure and surface area [15]². Hachisu and Suzuki developed smart bracelets to connect interpersonal touch with vibrotactile feedback [16]. The *Expressive Wearable* [17] uses, among other measurements, proximity sensors to express the wearer’s attitude; although designed for social interaction, it uses visual feedback and does not utilise the body as an interface. *TONG* [18] uses optical proximity sensors and visual feedback to remind people of interpersonal distance.

¹ Sometimes called couple’s therapy or couple’s counseling.

² TOUCHME by playtronica (<https://playtronica.com/>) is a commercial product for sonifying touch, but is not the subject of academic research.

Although optical sensors like Microsoft’s *Kinect* or Intel’s *RealSense* and standard proximity sensors (e.g. ultrasonic or infrared-based) can detect proximity, they rely on a clear field of vision and measurements at discrete points. Therefore, they are less convenient for social interaction, which requires freedom of movement independent of sensor positioning. Bian et al. however has developed a magnetic field proximity sensor for social distancing, which measures sensor-to-sensor distance rather than inter-body proximity [19].

Sentire overcomes the limitations and problems introduced by measuring proximity at discrete points, since the body itself becomes part of a sensor system that works regardless of the location of the measurement and orientation of the body in the space. The wired version of Sentire is based on a sensor system developed by Jonathan Reus³ and the *Metabody* project [20]. This prototype was further developed for the participatory performance series *Sentire*, which had been presented at numerous international festivals and events [21], before it finally evolved into an academic research project.

2.2 Inter-body coupling

Sentire’s wireless proximity sensors rely on electro-quasistatic coupling between two human bodies. The phenomenon of the human body to electrically couple—which occurs because of its conductivity—is researched across disciplines. The focus is usually on *intra-body communication*⁴ (IBC)—signals transmitted inside the same human body [22, 23]—or on the coupling between humans and objects [24–26]. Other related research focuses on the characteristics of the human body as an antenna [27, 28], the transmission of digitally encoded information in *body-to-body sensor networks* (BBNs) [29] and the preconditions and properties of the body as a communication channel [30].

To our best knowledge, at the time of writing, we are the first to exploit and research the effect of inter-body coupling for proximity sensing in the academic context. Grosse-Puppenthal et al. investigate capacitive near-field communication for ubiquitous interaction between persons and everyday objects [25]. A similar approach uses wrist-worn capacitive sensors to detect human touch, proximity and activity but is limited to movement-based actions between humans and objects [26].

Nath et al. [31] were the first, to their knowledge, to develop a theory of human inter-body coupling relying on *electro-quasistatic human body communication* (EQS-HBC). Their model serves as a theoretical framework to understand the mechanism behind the wireless proximity sensor we developed. Figure 1 illustrates the electro-quasistatic (capacitive) coupling between two human bodies as described in [31]. Although Nath et al. investigate inter-body coupling for analysis of security and interference properties in EQS-HBC, as opposed to describing its potential for proximity sensing, their theory and findings apply to the use of Sentire. Nath et al. provide a simplified circuit model

Figure 1. Capacitive inter-body coupling. Adapted from [31] which uses floating electrodes for EQS HBC; for Sentire’s proximity sensing we use electrodes attached to the shoes.

from which they derive an expression for the channel loss with a capacitive load at the receiver (R_x) and frequencies below 1MHz:

$$\frac{V_o}{V_i} \approx \frac{C_{G,Tx}}{C_B} \cdot \frac{C_C}{C_B} \cdot \frac{C_{G,Rx}}{C_L} \quad (1)$$

Where $C_{G,Tx}$ and $C_{G,Rx}$ denote the capacitance between ground electrodes and ground at the transmitter (T_x), respectively, the receiver (R_x); C_B , is the capacitance of the bodies coupling with the environment, C_C is the capacitance between the two bodies and C_L is the capacitive load at the receiver. The coupling capacitance C_C depends on the distance of the two human bodies and therefore is proportional to the channel loss:

$$\frac{V_o}{V_i} \sim C_C \quad (2)$$

Consequently, the measured voltage V_o at the receiver can be used to derive an inter-body proximity signal as described in the following section.

3. DEVELOPMENT

3.1 Technical Implementation

The foundation and starting point for developing the wireless proximity detection was an existing version of the Sentire sensor system, which uses two audio cables and conductive bracelets in conjunction with a consumer-grade audio interface and custom-developed software written in SuperCollider. Although in both the wired and wireless versions the physical phenomenon of capacitive coupling

³ <https://jonathanreus.com>

⁴ Sometimes referred to as human body communication (HBC). For a review of research on HBC, refer to Zhao et al. [22].

enables proximity sensing—i.e. the detection of distance and touch between the two human bodies—only substantial new hard- and software development rendered a wireless prototype possible. Before we describe the technical details and the primary efforts in the iterative process, we here provide an overview of the technical implementation.

Figure 2. Schematic diagram of Sentire, including—from top to bottom—the wireless proximity hardware (blue), the sensor data processing (yellow) and sound generation (red).

Figure 2 illustrates the various components and indicates the signal path of our closed-loop interactive interface. The interacting persons (“Person 1” and “Person 2”) wear custom-developed electronic devices (“Sentire Transceiver”) connected through body electrodes on their skin. Furthermore, they wear so-called “Ground Electrodes” attached to the soles of their shoes. We use a signal generator and an amplifier to feed an electrical signal through the body electrode into Person 1 (called the transmitter for convenience). As described in section 2.2, capacitive coupling of the two bodies causes a signal transmission to the receiver (Person 2), whereby the return path of the signal goes through the ground electrodes, which capacitively cou-

ple with the environmental ground. The strength of the received and amplified signal depends on the distance between the receiver and the transmitter (simplified, one can think of two capacitor plates). We utilise this “proximity effect” to generate a control signal, which changes linearly with the distance of the two bodies. The transceiver at the receiver amplifies the transmitted sensor signal and sends it to a base station via digital radio. To obtain and linearise the control signal in the digital domain, we use our software written in *SuperCollider*. These digital signal processing (DSP) stages that convert the “raw” sensor signal into a proximity and touch signal are part of the proximity sensor (i.e. the gestural input) and are described in more detail in section 4. In contrast, despite using the same software framework, the sonification stage is part of the sound generator following the classical definition of digital musical instruments [32]. Mapping the proximity signal to selected parameters of an algorithmic sound synthesis process and providing auditory feedback through a sound system finally enables closed-loop auditory interaction.

3.2 Hardware Development

The iterative hardware development of the Sentire prototypes (“transceiver”) was foremost influenced by the need to enable wireless proximity and touch sensing comparable in range and reactivity to the wired Sentire system. A second premise was the usability of the prototype in the context of couple therapy [33]. Besides implementing the technical requirements, this necessity also meant designing wearable and failsafe prototypes for our real-world studies. The limited technical and human resources required us to focus on a straightforward and pragmatic design. The individual components were kept as modular as possible to enable parallel development and save resources. After testing different platforms and frameworks in the first iteration, we decided to use a *Teensy 3.2* microcontroller development board, together with an *SGTL5000* Audio Codec. The *Teensy* board offers flexibility and fulfils the requirements for most of the wireless sensor components (signal generator, signal receiver, radio transmitter and base station). Another advantage of using the same microcontroller platform for different purposes is to minimise the development effort (e.g. PCB design and part sourcing only needs to be done once instead of three times). The prototypes are powered by a *250mAh Li-Po* battery.

3.2.1 Transceiver Board

Figure 3a shows the developed Sentire transceiver board assembled with a *Teensy 3.2*, an *SGTL5000* Audio Codec and an *nRF24L01+* radio module for the wireless transmission between the receiver and the base station. The transceiver board is used in different stages of the wireless sensor system (see figure 2): (1) At the transmitter, generating the transmitter signal; (2) at the receiver, amplifying the received signal and sending it to the base station via radio; (3) at the base station, receiving the “raw” sensor signal.

Figure 3. Sentire transceiver (a) and signal amplifier (b) circuit boards.

3.2.2 Signal Amplifier

One way to improve the maximum distance of the proximity detection is to increase the power of the transmission signal. The signal amplifier’s operating voltage and gain factor determine the maximum peak-to-peak voltage at its output and, therefore, the transmission signal’s power. The regulated output of the Teensy Board delivers 3.3V (at a maximum of 250mA). Using a DC-DC step up converter based on the *MT3608* chip (up to 30V) and in conjunction with a *PAM8006ATR* class-d amplifier (8 to 18V supply) allowed for an increase of 14.7dB in signal strength compared to using the regulated output of the microcontroller (see figure 3b). Another attempt to increase the transmission power was made by running at 3.3V operating voltage and using a transformer at the output of the amplifier. Although we could increase the output voltage, the transformer itself caused an unwanted side effect: direct coupling between transformer and receiver, and, therefore, disabled proximity detection based on capacitive inter-body coupling.

3.2.3 Electrodes

One of the biggest challenges in developing the prototype as a wearable was designing and manufacturing suitable ground electrodes. We assume that the ground electrodes form a parallel-plate capacitor with the ground and therefore the following formula applies:

$$C = \epsilon_0 \epsilon_r \cdot \frac{A}{d} \quad (3)$$

Where A is the surface of the electrode and d corresponds to the distance between ground electrode and physical ground. From (3) follows:

$$C_G \sim \frac{A}{d} \quad (4)$$

And with equation (1) from section 2.2 furthermore:

$$\frac{V_o}{V_i} \sim \left(\frac{A}{d}\right)^2 \quad (5)$$

This means the transmission ratio $\frac{V_o}{V_i}$ is proportional to the square of ground electrode area A and inversely proportional to the square of distance d between ground electrode and ground. Consequently, one premise was to maximise A and minimise d . On the basis of rapid prototyping and qualitative user tests, several requirements were set:

1. Electrodes are attached to the shoes (this requirement arose from the context of couple therapy, where some clients find it unpleasant to take off their shoes)
2. Minimum distance d , made possible by attaching the ground electrode to the shoe soles and minimising the thickness of the overlay material
3. Thin yet sturdy and non-slippery overlay material
4. Tight grip on the shoe
5. Flexible fixture to fit different shoe forms and sizes
6. Feasibility with the given resources of the project

Several iterations of material research and prototype testing resulted in an electrode based on silicone injection moulding and flexible conductive fabric. In an attempt to design a single-component foot electrode, we used *single-walled carbon nanotubes* (SWNCTs) as an additive (1 percent) to the *liquid silicone rubber* (LSR). The blended SWNCTs make the rubber itself conductive yet maintain its flexibility. Although this iteration served as a proof of concept, we rejected it because we could not estimate the material’s biocompatibility and health risks.⁵ Therefore, we used the previous iteration of silicone electrodes. The moulds for both electrode iterations were made from *polylactic acid* (PLA) using a *fused deposition modelling* (FDM) 3D-Printer.

While describing all the technical details of the production process goes beyond the scope of this paper, it’s worth noting here that the body electrodes had relatively few requirements compared to the ground electrodes described above, and were thus relatively easy to implement. After using standard *electromyography* (EMG) electrodes in the first iterations, we designed body electrodes based on flexible conductive fabric and velcro (see figure 4).

Figure 4. Sentire wireless prototype.

4. SOFTWARE DEVELOPMENT

The custom Sentire software was written in SuperCollider and handles an essential part of the wireless proximity de-

⁵ Studies indicate high bioaccumulation [34] and possibly asbestos-like toxicity [35].

tection. Though developed in parallel and as part of the software, the specific parameter mapping and implementation of our algorithmic sound environments are not described in detail in this paper.

Figure 5. Digital signal processing (DSP) chain for obtaining the proximity and touch signals.

Figure 5 shows the DSP chain from the received “raw” sensor signal to the obtained proximity (and touch) signal, mapped to an algorithmic sound environment. To extract the transmitted signal and remove noise, the chain filters the sensor signal twice (bandpass and slew filter). Then, an envelope follower detects the amplitude and gains an exponential control signal dependent on proximity. Two further DSP blocks smooth (“Exponential Lag Filter”), linearise and scale (“Scaling Function”) the signal and yield a linear, normalised control signal.

One major disadvantage of relying on ground electrodes is the strong dependency of the signal strength on distance d (see formula (5)). Thus, raising the foot will cause the signal amplitude to drop and, as a result, falsify the proximity signal. Our attempt to compensate for this effect is to use two receivers and two transmitters, one attached to each foot. We applied a bandpass filter to the signals sensed at the receivers using the individual transmitter signal frequency to return four sensor signals. Assuming that at least one foot is always on the ground, we select the strongest sensor signal for proximity detection. Yet, duplicating the sensor hardware introduced another problem: cross-coupling between transmitters and receivers. Table 1 shows the resulting influence of raising a single foot on the four sensor signal channels.

	Signals at receiver one (R_1)		Signals at receiver two (R_2)	
	S_1	S_2	S_3	S_4
$R_1 \uparrow$	down+	down+	up	up
$R_2 \uparrow$	up	up	down+	down+
$T_1 \uparrow$	down+	up	down+	up
$T_2 \uparrow$	up	down+	up	down+

Table 1. Influence of raising individual feet on the four sensor signal channels (S_1 – S_4)

Raising one foot at the receiver side (e.g. $R_1 \uparrow$) strongly dampens (“down+”) the sensed signals (S_1 and S_2) on this side, while it raises (“up”) the sensed signals at the second receiver (other foot, S_3 and S_4). The other receiver changes the signals analogously. In contrast, raising one foot at the transmitter side (e.g. $T_1 \uparrow$) strongly dampens signal one (S_1) at receiver one (R_1) and signal three (S_3) at receiver two (R_2), while lifting signal two (S_2) at receiver one (R_1) and signal four (S_4) at receiver two (R_2). Because every combination of changes is mutually exclusive, we can algorithmically detect distinct foot movements (up, down) and

distinguish them from proximity changes. Using thresholds for fast changes makes the process more robust. The algorithm compensates for the influence of footsteps to a great extent by multiplying the individual signals with correction factors that have been determined empirically.

5. FOSTERING SOCIAL INTERACTION THROUGH SOUND FEEDBACK

The sonification of proximity and touch as used for Sentire is influenced mainly by the experience with the system in the artistic context of participatory performances. Within the interdisciplinary Project “Social Interaction through Sound Feedback,” our sonic interaction design had a strong focus on clinical and non-clinical therapeutic use cases.

In line with [36], we call the set of parameters that defines the sonic quality a “sound environment” (SE) [37]. A SE results from predefined artistic decisions concerning sound design and algorithmic composition combined with a specific parameter mapping. Sentire’s SEs shape the interactive experience. We therefore developed the SEs by focusing on kinaesthetic perception—i.e., perception of one’s own movements—and by intensifying the interaction in the intimate and personal space. According to Joseph Rován et al.’s definition of parameter mappings [38], we use a “divergent” mapping that links a one-dimensional gestural parameter (proximity) to multiple musical parameters simultaneously [37].

Sentire provides several different SEs with distinct sound qualities ranging from atmospheric and tonal sounds to percussive and rhythmic, each aiming to sonically intensify the acts of approach and touch. We developed an SE for our couple therapy study based on the physical modelling of singing bowls. The interaction usually starts with silence and at a distance of about $3m$. As the participants move closer, the sound’s amplitude rises; furthermore, the fundamental frequencies’ distribution and harmonics shift from slightly inharmonic ratios (e.g. 3:4, or perfect fourth) to more harmonic intervals (e.g. 2:3, or perfect fifth). Touch events stop the continuous sound generation and trigger one of three chords (Cm9, Fm11 and Ebmaj9) together with pseudo-random sequences derived from the tone material of these three chords (without C and D, spanning two octaves). Consequently, the first note played determines the musical mode. We source the sounds for touch sonification from Fender Rhodes (chords) and Celli (melody) synthesizers implemented in SuperCollider. Sustained touches keep the melody playing, while the duration of touch alters the tempo of the played notes.

The couple therapy sessions served both as a framework for usability testing and to investigate the relationship between sound, sociality and therapy, combining Structured Observation and Microphenomenological Interviews. It is worth noting that our wireless technology for the sonification of proximity and touch can be used in a broad range of interactive musical applications. Sending the proximity signal via *Open Sound Control* (OSC) allows any software which can receive OSC messages to map the interactions to musical parameters.

Figure 6. From top to bottom: Theoretical and measured exponential sensor values; theoretical linear values and measured values mapped from exponential to linear; error between theoretical values and measured values mapped to linear.

6. EVALUATION AND DISCUSSION

Within the interdisciplinary context of the research project, we developed new sensor technology for the sonification of proximity and touch. We built working and scalable wireless prototypes to be used in real-world and clinical research. The question of how interaction is facilitated through real-time auditory feedback is investigated by applying behavioural analysis using structured observation [37]. Our practical experience with Sentire in an waiting-list controlled trial in couple therapy emphasises the improved flexibility gained through the wireless version. Remaining undisturbed by cables attached to the body enables more freedom of movement; in addition, the less “visible” the technological system becomes for users, the more it may enable individuals to use it as therapeutic means for uncovering the intricacies of social interaction.

6.1 Performance

The sensor system can measure proximity up to approximately $4m$. Above this range, noise starts to shadow the measurement. Figure 6.1 shows proximity measurements in the range from $0cm$ to $400cm$, taken every $10cm$. The sensor values are normalised to the values at minimum ($0cm$) and maximum ($400cm$) distance. Furthermore, the figure compares the measured values—mapped from exponential to linear—with a theoretical linear trend and the resulting error. The mapping from exponential to linear could be optimised; however, qualitative tests indicate that more accurate curve fittings are rather hard to perceive in the sonification.

Based on the systematic investigation of different modes of inter-body coupling by Zhao et al. [31], we hypothesize that shifting to a frequency range above $10MHz$ —the range of electro-magnetic coupling as opposed to electro-

quasistatic coupling—would extend the possible range. Currently, we use an adaptive exponential lag filter to counterbalance the increasing noise in the far range. Although the sensing range of the wireless prototype suits the typical interactive space and is similar to the wired version of Sentire, shifting to a higher frequency domain would also make the system less susceptible to environmental noise; consequently, less filtering would be needed, and the system’s reactivity could be improved. The filter has a lag time of $0.6s$ in the far range to $1ms$ for close distances. These settings are in line with our assumption that the system’s reactivity is more relevant in the intimate space.

Since our proximity sensing is based on electro-quasistatic coupling, and the human bodies do not only couple with each other and the ground, but also with the environment, factors such as body size, floor material and nearby electrical devices can influence results. Nonetheless, the audible differences in the sonification are minor and not significantly relevant, as the users’ perception is focused on changes in proximity rather than the precise measurement of physical distance and its representation in the sound environment. Since the contact surface slightly alters the signal strength when touching, a separate signal processing for values above the touch threshold could render a quantitative touch detection possible. However, at this stage of development, our software does not implement this feature yet.

6.2 Development Considerations

A central challenge in the hardware development was to overcome the need for a common ground connection as used in the wired version of Sentire. Our solution, custom-developed ground electrodes attached to shoe soles, required a considerable amount of product design and introduced the need to compensate for foot movement. While we have shown that using two independent prototypes per user and a dedicated algorithm can eliminate the influence of foot movement to a large extent, the solution doubles the technical overhead. Furthermore, the assumption that only one foot is raised at a time limits the compensation effect in real-case scenarios. Our latest iteration of foot electrodes based on SWCNTs as an additive to silicone served as proof-of-concept for manufacturing conductive electrodes that can be worn on shoe soles. However, these had to be rejected because of the unknown health risks of the materials.

Using a serial protocol for the transmission of the sensor signal to the base station is beneficial in terms of latency, but prone to losing packets and thus interferes with a stable proximity detection. However, because we will shift most of the sensor processing from SuperCollider to an embedded platform as part of the wearable, such interference is a minimal concern. The Teensy 3.2 microcontroller board and its software libraries turned out to be a pragmatic all-in-one solution for our evaluation boards, but future iterations should prioritise size and power efficiency and therefore implement a minimalistic solution in favour of wearability and usability. The current prototype iteration weighs approx. 320 grams in total (two times Electronics, Foot

Electrodes and Body Electrodes) and the main electronic parts (including the case, excluding the connectors) have a size of approx. $5\text{cm} \times 5\text{cm} \times 2.5\text{cm}$ (transceiver) and $5\text{cm} \times 5\text{cm} \times 1\text{cm}$ (signal amplifier) each. Battery life is mainly limited by the energy consumption of the signal amplifiers and, without any optimization, lasts for about 2 hours.

7. CONCLUSIONS AND OUTLOOK

We developed a new wireless sensor technology capable of measuring proximity and touch that overcomes the limitations of established systems for inter-body distance detection. The system has a range of approximately four metres and therefore covers the three relevant interpersonal zones as defined by Hall [1]: intimate, personal and social. Quantitative comparisons between the two systems will be the subject of our subsequent user study.

It is worth noting that, apart from closed-loop auditory interaction, the developed sensor technology could be used in a broad range of clinical and non-clinical applications. Furthermore, it is not limited to sensing proximity between individuals. Future usage could involve the detection of proximity between entities in general, including objects, provided they are conductive and sizable enough for affixing sensor electronics.

So far, a qualitative comparison shows the same effectiveness as the wired version of the system in couple therapy and, importantly, highlights the possibility of greater freedom in movement and thus improved usability.

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